

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue I | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

DR. KRESTER M. DIAZ

Assistant Professor IV

Negros Oriental State University

kresterm Diaz@gmail.com

“CAN YOU LOSE YOUR FIRST LANGUAGE? A CRITICAL REVIEW ON FIRST LANGUAGE ATTRITION OF MORPHOSYNTAX IN ADULT BILINGUALS”

Language acquisition, in a general sense, is a process of learning a native or a second language by which humans acquire to comprehend the internal structure of a system (language) which its units (words), in turn, can be assembled into a wide variety of infinite combinations (sentences).

Studying how word meaning, sentence meaning, and discourse meaning are computed and represented in the mind has given me very remarkable and valuable insights into the merging worlds of linguistics and psychology that I thought at first was never even possible.

The crux of studying *Psycholinguistics* circles significantly around the three investigated primary language processes and language knowledge such as language comprehension, language production, and language acquisition: specifically, it provides an exhaustive discussions on how our students produce and recognize speech, how they perceive words, letters, and sentences, how they can improve texts to make them easier to understand, how they learn and recall information from texts, and how the brain functions to process language, just to mention a few. It is always noteworthy to note that the crucial fact for understanding the place of language in human cognition is its diversity and how this affects students' processing of language. On acquiring the first language, one of the earliest scientific explanations of language acquisition was provided by Skinner (1957). As one of the pioneers of behaviorism, he accounted for language development by means of environmental influence (Lemetyinen, 2012). That is, language is acquired through principles of conditioning, including association, imitation, and reinforcement.

On the other hand, the world's most famous linguist to date, Chomsky, in Da Cruz (2015) heavily criticized Skinner's account and argued that children's ability to learn language is due to genetically programmed organ that is located in the brain. In other words, children immediately start to develop a language once they are born and involved in any linguistic environments since language is hardwired into their brains. Despite Chomsky's detailed, polemical and persuasive arguments, his innateness hypothesis, which he believes to be the only coherent and plausible one that has yet been proposed to account for the acquisition of language, has still received criticisms by a number of radical critics saying that the theory of Chomsky lacks sufficient evidences. The “nurture vs. nature” issue on language acquisition is still prevalent and is still debated by a number of scholars at present.

Moreover, on acquiring the second language, Krashen's well-accepted theory has so much to say on this. Krashen (2013) ascertains that language acquisition occurs subconsciously. He also made it clear learners acquire (not learn) the parts of a language in a predictable order (i.e. Some grammatical items, for example, are acquired early while others are acquired later).

Furthermore, second language acquisition takes place at any period of one's life after the mother tongue has been (largely) acquired. In other words, all new second language learners progress through the same five predictable stages, to wit: Pre-production, Early production, Speech emergence, Intermediate fluency, and Advanced fluency.

Schmid and Kopke (2014) in their study Bilingualism and Attrition speculated that the possibility of the brain to change certain biological properties in the process of maturation when acquiring a second language since the acquisition and knowledge of a first language is believed to occupy a privileged status in the human mind. They also posited the idea of first language attrition when L1 comes into contact with L2 with a number of necessary conditions in order for the L1 attrition to set in like emigration, extensive use of the L2 in daily life, extremely reduced use of the L1 in daily life, plus a fairly long time span (decades).

The purpose of this paper is to investigate specific process of change in the first language that may be particularly vulnerable to L1 attrition if exposed to a dominant L2 that all bilinguals undergo to some degree. From the insights provided above, this paper would like to find out the difficulties that are encountered when acquiring and learning the second language in the environment of the first language by disambiguating the following issues:

1. ***What will happen when L1 learners acquire a second language?***
2. ***Is L1 morphosyntax vulnerable to L2 effects?***
3. ***When L2 comes into contact, will there be an L1 attrition of morphosyntax in adult bilinguals?***

The crux of the matter is that whether or not, bilingual learners' L1 processing will experience difficulties after an extended stay in the L2 environment that might impact L1 attrition.

Language Attrition

Language attrition, in the words of Schmid and De Bot (2005), is often considered to be a reversal of language acquisition: where language acquisition is a process during which the proficiency in a first or second language increases, in the process of language attrition, lack of contact leads to a reduced level of proficiency in the attriting language.

Gurel (2008) in his article presented a selective review of previous research findings on morphosyntactic attrition in the first language (L1) grammar of adult bilinguals. His review article aims to identify unstable areas of the L1 morphosyntax that are more likely to undergo attrition in language contact situations, and to discuss the impact of a dominant L2 as a possible cause of this grammatical change in the L1. Gurel cited Cok (2002) who pointed out that:

The two languages are schematized within an integration continuum that ranges from total separation to total integration. The relationship between the L1 and L2 might change from one domain to another. It is also possible that, even within the same linguistic domain, the integration continuum might apply to linguistic features differentially.

The above plausible premise sums up the idea of L1 morphosyntactic attrition since the L1's morphosyntactic properties do not have exact equivalence to L2's induced change.

Syntactic Attrition

To support the claim that L1 syntactic features have been greatly affected due to the dominant L2 contact, Gurel, in search of **syntactic attrition**, discussed L1 data from Turkish speakers who were exposed to English in adulthood and who have been living in North America for a prolonged period of time. Findings revealed that L1 attrition is very evident in binding properties of overt and null pronouns in pro-drop L1 Turkish under the influence of non-pro drop L2 English. According to Gurel, this is said to be a clear effect of L2 English because in constructions such as *Murat_i onun*_i sinemaya gidecegini söyledi* ('Murat_i said that he would go to the movies'), the Turkish overt pronoun *o*, unlike the English pronoun *he* cannot be coreferential with the sentential subject. Hence, it was found out that the disjointness requirement of the overt pronoun *o* is not strictly followed by L1 attriters due to L2 English.

Benjamins et.al in their book *Language Attrition* cited Gurel who interpreted his results in the context of the subset-superset relations of the L1 and L2, stating that in the context of L1 attrition where the 'influenceing language' (i.e. L2) is the superset of the affected language' (i.e. L1), more signs of L2 transfer into the L1 grammar are noticeable, resulting in more attrition effects.

Another study conducted by Wang (2007) on Syntactic Attrition where he identified selected Chinese syntactic structures that underwent the most and the least attrition shed light to the present study. Results indicated that over time the syntactic structure of punctual time adverbials suffered the least attrition, while the verb copying for quantity adverbial phrases had the greatest attrition. From the analysis of these structures, Wang explained that the frequency of use and the language training of the subjects allowed the subjects to overcome, for at least a few years, the attrition that usually results because of language distance. On the L1 Attrition of the Spanish present tense, Cuza (2010) examined the potential native language attrition value among long-term Spanish immigrants. Results showed low levels of acceptance and use of present-tense forms with an ongoing meaning by the immigrant group, as well as significantly higher use of the progressive form. He further argued that transfer from English selectional properties has reduced the range of lexical selection of the Spanish present, leading to convergence toward the most restrictive L2 configuration.

However, on the basis of assumptions regarding syntactic modularity, Filliaci et.al. (2004) conducted a study on the effects of syntactic attrition on the L1 of Greek and Italian speakers of English who have achieved near-native proficiency in their L2 (English) but still use their L1 on a regular basis. They reported that attrition effects are found in the production of preverbal subjects in the Greek group whereas Italian speakers show attrition effects in the interpretation of overt pronominal subjects. They argued that the results are in the right direction; that is, semantic features are vulnerable in language attrition whereas syntactic options remain intact.

Morphological Attrition

Pelc (2001) investigated first language attrition in Greek-English bilinguals where he identified three areas of attrition such as lexical, morpholexical, and morphosyntactic domains of greek. She stated in her paper that the rejection of Greek grammatical sentences and acceptance of English grammatical sentences characterize the attrited state of these bilinguals.

In the mophological area, Pelc found out that the morphologically complex gender system which extends to the article, noun, adjective, and pronoun is vulnerable to attrition in Greek when it is in contact with a language such as English.

In addition, Schmid's (2004) findings largely confirm that L1 attrition among German Jews who emigrated to Anglophone countries showed that interlanguage effects of German morphology under L2 influence of English are hard to establish since there were only a small number of interferences, for instance, in plural allomorphy and agreement including, for example, plural marking. She hypothesized that the loss of morphological features may eventually result in a move from synthetic structures to more regularized or analytic ones.

Another study conducted by Hakansson (1995) where she explored the attrition of different aspects of Swedish grammar indicates that bilingual students' noun phrase morphology had undergone attrition.

Furthermore, a study about the first language loss in Spanish-speaking children was detailed by Anderson (2012) where she presented a list of patterns of first language (L1) loss/attrition due to language shift or language contact situations. Below is Anderson's presentation of L1 loss.

Patterns	Example
<i>Morphological</i>	
Noun phrase	El casa rojo/la casa roja (the red house [masculine]; the red house [feminine])
Gender agreement errors Verbal morphology/verb phrase	Yo camina/Yo camino (I walk [third person singular]/ I walk [first person singular])
Person/number errors	Ellos come/ Ellos comen (They eat)
Use of third-person singular default form	(see above example)
Aspectual errors (perfect/imperfect substitution)	Yo fui/ Yo iba (I went/ I used to go [implying habitual action])

Taxonomy of cross-linguistic influence, according to which L1 – L2 contact might lead to processes was provided by Pavlenko in Gurel (2008). He enumerated the following changes when L1-L2 contact begins such as:

- borrowing: addition of L2 elements to the L1;
- restructuring: deletion of certain L1 rules and/or incorporation of L2 elements into L1 resulting in substitutions or simplifications;
- convergence: creation of a unitary system, distinct from both L1 and L2;

- shift: a move from L1 structure to approximate L2 structures;
- attrition: loss of some L1 elements due to L2.

Having reviewed and discussed several studies pertinent to the first language attrition of morphosyntax in adult bilinguals, Gurel (2007) concluded that restructuring of the L1 grammar is possible due to extensive L2 exposure combined with less accessible L1 input; when L1 and L2 have no corresponding forms, the L2 form with all its morphosyntactic features can override the L1 form that is not used as frequently; when L1 and L2 have no corresponding forms, L2-interference dependent change is not relevant; and complex L1 forms might be processed with difficulty as a result of long-term disuse.

All these claims run parallel to the findings of Pelc (2001). Her findings revealed that notably, the L2 use affects L1 competence in terms of its morphosyntactic domain.

Research results suggest that L1 attrition of morphosyntax among adult bilinguals is possible in language contact situations. The impact of a dominant L2 during the acquisition process makes L1 morphosyntax vulnerable in its effects that bring forth dramatic language attrition in the L1.

Teaching Implications

First language attrition of morphosyntax is still a fertile terrain for research.

With all the towering importance of these linguistic and psycholinguistic accounts of language transition in the context of language acquisition and attrition, language teachers should develop the necessary target language skills of the students by not spewing away the use of mother tongue especially when students utilize that social facility to express themselves in a verbatim manner. Language teachers should address the needs of typical language learners experiencing language loss during language performance assessment. They have to completely understand the cause of language attrition so they could plan/design any intervention programs/activities that consider both cultural and linguistic diversity and will provide students to use language in contexts if deemed necessary.

References

- Anderson, R. (2012). First Language Loss in Spanish-Speaking Children. *Retrieved from* www.archive.brookespublishing.com
- Benjamins, J. (2007). Language Attrition. *Retrieved from* www.books.google.com
- Cuza, A. (2010). On the L1 Attrition of the Spanish Present Tense. *Retrieved from* www.ics.purdue.edu
- Da Cruz, Z. (2015). First Language Acquisition. *Retrieved from* www.skemman.is
- Filliaci, F. et.al. (2004). First Language Attrition and Syntactic Subjects: A study of Greek and Italian near-native speakers of English. *Retrieved from* www.journals.safepub.com
- Hakansson, G. (1995). Syntax and Morphology in Language Attrition: A study of Five Bilingual Expatriate Swedes. *Retrieved from* www.onlinelibrary.wiley.com

Krashen, S. (2013). Second Language Acquisition. *Retrieved from* www.sdkrashen.com

Lemetyinen, H. (2012). Language Acquisition Theory. *Retrieved from* www.simplypsychology.org

Linda, P. (2001). L1 Lexical, Morphological and Morphosyntactic Attrition in Greek English Bilinguals. *Retrieved from* www.academicworks.cuny.edu

Malone, S. (2012). Theories and Research of Second Language Acquisition. *Retrieved from* www.sil.org

Schmid, M. et.al. (2004). First Language Attrition. *Retrieved from* www.books.google.com

Schmid, M. & Kopke, B. (2014). Bilingualism and Attrition. *Retrieved from* www.hal-univ-tlse2.com

